

First HPTLC method for the simultaneous quantification of tacrolimus, sirolimus and mycophenolate mofetil from their pharmaceutical formulations and biological samples[†]

Jui J. Pandya^a, Vijay D. Chavada^a, Nejal M. Bhatt^a, Mallika Sanyal^b and Pranav S. Shrivastav^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, School of Sciences, Gujarat University, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad-380 009, Gujarat, India

E-mail : pranav_shrivastav@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, St. Xavier's College, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad-380 009, Gujarat, India

Abstract : A simple, accurate and precise high-performance thin-layer chromatographic (HPTLC) method has been developed and validated for the simultaneous quantification of immunosuppressant drugs, tacrolimus (TAC), sirolimus (SRL) and mycophenolate mofetil (MMF) in their pharmaceutical formulations and also from biological samples. Planar chromatographic separation was performed on aluminium-backed layer of silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ using a mixture of toluene-acetonitrile-glacial acetic acid (7.0 : 2.9 : 0.1, v/v/v) as the mobile phase. Densitometric determination of the separated spots was done at 210 nm. The *R_f* values obtained under the optimized conditions were 0.61 ± 0.02, 0.50 ± 0.02 and 0.38 ± 0.01 for TAC, SRL and MMF respectively. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for linearity, accuracy and precision, recovery, repeatability and robustness. Linearity of the method was established in the range of 500–4000 ng/band for TAC and SRL and 200–1500 ng/band for MMF. The LOD/LOQ were 16.97/51.59, 41.99/127.22 and 25.22/76.42 ng/band for TAC, SRL and MMF respectively. Their % assay from tablet formulation was 100.08%, 98.90% and 99.88% respectively. TAC and SRL were extracted from human whole blood by solid phase extraction on Lichrosep Sequence cartridge, while MMF was separated from human plasma following protein precipitation with acetonitrile. The mean recovery of TAC, SRL and MMF from biological fluids was 93.48%, 94.69% and 96.52% respectively. The stability of the analytes in whole blood/plasma was established under different storage conditions.

Keywords : Tacrolimus, sirolimus, mycophenolate mofetil, biological fluids, high performance thin layer chromatography, pharmaceutical formulations.

Introduction

Immunosuppressant drugs are mainly used for the prophylaxis of allograft rejection in solid organ transplant recipients^{1,2}. These include calcineurin inhibitors, cyclosporine and tacrolimus (TAC), mammalian target of rapamycin inhibitors, sirolimus (SRL) and everolimus and a non-competitive reversible inhibitor of inosine monophosphate dehydrogenase, mycophenolic acid which is the active metabolite of mycophenolate mofetil (MMF)^{1,3,4}. These are referred to as critical dose drugs with narrow therapeutic index. An overdosing of these drugs can lead to serious toxicity and long term morbidity while under dosing can result in organ rejection⁵.

TAC (Fig. 1A), a macrolide lactone produced by the

fungus *Streptomyces tsukubaensis* was initially used during liver transplant. It is now routinely used in the management of kidney, heart, pancreas, small bowel, lung and bone marrow transplants^{6–8}. It acts by binding to a cytoplasmic protein, immunophilin and the resultant complex then inhibits the function of an intracellular protein calcineurin. This interaction leads to inhibition of T-lymphocyte signal transduction and decreases interleukin (IL)-2 transcription which gives rise to immune suppression^{7–9}. Due to variability in the absorption and clearance of TAC very low levels are found in human plasma. Thus, monitoring of the drug in whole blood is recommended to achieve optimal therapeutic efficacy, while minimizing the risk of toxicity⁷.

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

SRL (Fig. 1B) is a potent non-calcineurin inhibiting immunosuppressant having antiproliferative properties. It has a unique mechanism of action which is different from the calcineurin inhibitors. It is commonly used with calcineurin inhibitors like TAC and cyclosporine A or MMF for the prophylaxis of organ rejection in organ transplant patients¹⁰. Although SRL possesses structural similarity with TAC, their mechanism of action is quite different^{10,11}. Like TAC, SRL binds with FKBP¹², a ubiquitous abundant protein that acts as a receptor for the immunosuppressant drug, however; the SRL-FKBP12 complex has no effect on calcineurin phosphatase unlike TAC. Instead it binds with one or more proteins known as mammalian targets of rapamycin and thus inhibits both DNA and protein synthesis, resulting in obstruction of the cell cycle in late G1 phase as it progresses to the S phase^{12,13}. As a result, SRL reduces T-cell activation at a later stage in the cell cycle than the calcineurin inhibitors by inhibiting cytokine-induced signal transduction pathways, leading to the suppression of IL-2 and IL-4 driven T-cell proliferation¹⁴.

Prodrug MMF (Fig. 1C) is a widely used immunosuppressant drug and is also prescribed in the treatment of

autoimmune disease^{15,16}. It is a selective, reversible and non-competitive inhibitor of inosine monophosphate dehydrogenase (IMPDH), the rate limiting enzyme in the *de novo* synthesis of guanosine nucleotides¹⁷. It gets completely and rapidly hydrolyzed by esterases to mycophenolic acid (MPA), the active metabolite of MMF. As it has a different mechanism of action, it is used in combination therapy with calcineurin inhibitors.

Methods reported for their determination are based either on immunoassays or chromatographic techniques. The major limitation of immunoassays is the non-specific binding of the antibody to the immunosuppressant drugs and endogenous compounds which results in overestimation of their concentration^{1,6}. Several methods have been reported for the individual determination of TAC¹⁸⁻²⁵, SRL²⁶⁻³² and MMF/MPA³³⁻⁴⁰ using spectrophotometry^{18,33}, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)^{19,26,27,34-36}, liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)^{20-23,28-31,37} and ultra performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS)^{24,25,32,38-40} in pharmaceutical formulations and biological fluids. Similarly, numerous methods are available for the simultaneous determination of TAC and SRL along with other immunosuppressant drugs⁴¹⁻⁴⁹.

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of (A) tacrolimus, (B) sirolimus and (C) mycophenolate mofetil.

Application of HPTLC for the analysis of immunosuppressant drugs has been a subject of very few reports. Literature presents only three methods for the individual determination of TAC⁵⁰ and MMF^{51,52} in pharmaceutical preparations or human plasma. Currently there is no HPTLC based method for SRL. Thus in the present work an HPTLC method has been developed for the simultaneous determination of TAC, SRL and MMF. This technique affords parallel analysis of multiple samples in a single run using small amount of solvents, thereby reducing the time and cost of analysis. All three drugs were estimated in their commercial formulations and also in biological fluids. The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines for linearity, sensitivity, selectivity, accuracy and precision, recovery and robustness⁵³.

Results and discussion

HPTLC method optimization :

For the selection of suitable wavelength for detection, standard solutions of TAC, SRL and MMF were prepared and their UV spectra were acquired. Upon assessment of overlain spectra of the drugs, it was observed that TAC had a peak maximum at 204 nm, SRL showed two major peaks at 207 nm and 280 nm, while MMF had three peaks at 216 nm, 250 nm and 305 nm as evident from Fig. 2. However, an optimum and reproducible response for all the analytes were obtained at 210 nm and hence was selected in the present work.

In order to have best mobile phase system for baseline separation of TAC, SRL and MMF, several mobile phase

systems were tested on aluminium-backed layer of silica gel 60 F₂₅₄. Moreover, it was expected that the three drugs should distribute themselves within the optimum R_f values from 0.20–0.80, which is generally considered as the most reproducible region. Methods for separate determination of TAC⁵⁰ and MMF^{51,52} have employed toluene-acetonitrile-glacial acetic acid (6.0 : 4.0 : 0.1, v/v/v) and triethylamine buffer (pH 5.3)-acetonitrile respectively as the eluting solvents on silica gel plates. In the present work, single as well as binary solvent mixtures having a wide range of eluting strengths were tested to optimize the best solvent system for all three analytes. During initial trials with single solvents namely methanol, acetonitrile, ethyl acetate, chloroform and toluene, TAC and SRL presented a similar elution pattern with very little difference in their R_f values (Table 1). Both the analytes showed greater retention in methanol ($R_f > 0.20$) compared to non-polar solvent toluene ($R_f > 0.40$). This behaviour was expected due to their structural similarity and physicochemical properties. Moreover, there was a gradual increase in R_f values with decrease in solvent polarity. On the other hand MMF gave a distinct spot in all the solvents, but with significant peak tailing. Based on these results, binary solvent mixtures of chloroform-methanol and chloroform-ethyl acetate were tested in different proportions. However, it was difficult to separate TAC and SRL and to control peak tailing for MMF. Nevertheless, encouraging results were found with toluene-acetonitrile binary system wherein some separation was possible between TAC and SRL. Subtle changes in the composition

Fig. 2. Zero-order UV spectra of tacrolimus (5.0 µg/mL), sirolimus (2.0 µg/mL) and mycophenolate mofetil (10 µg/mL) in methanol.

Table 1. Chromatographic trials with different eluting solvent systems on silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ TLC plates

Mobile phase	Retention factor, R_f			Observation
	TAC	SRL	MMF	
Methanol	0.15	0.12	0.41	No separation between TAC and SRL Peak tailing for MMF with poor peak shape
Acetonitrile	0.17	0.14	0.36	No separation between TAC and SRL Peak tailing for MMF
Ethyl acetate	0.21	0.19	0.32	No separation between any of the drugs Peak tailing for MMF
Chloroform	0.32	0.29	0.28	Poor chromatography No separation between any of the drugs
Toluene	0.44	0.43	0.24	No separation between TAC and SRL Little tailing for MMF
Chloroform-methanol (5 : 5, v/v)	0.40	0.37	0.18	No separation between TAC and SRL Little tailing for MMF
Chloroform-ethyl acetate (5 : 5, v/v)	0.25	0.22	0.13	Poor chromatography No separation between any of the drugs
Toluene-acetonitrile (5 : 5, v/v)	0.41	0.37	0.45	No baseline separation between any of the drugs Peak shape for MMF not acceptable
Toluene-acetonitrile (6 : 4, v/v)	0.52	0.49	0.41	No separation between TAC and SRL Slightly tailing for MMF peak
Toluene-acetonitrile (7 : 3, v/v)	0.60	0.51	0.37	Good spots for all three drugs with baseline resolution Very slight peak tailing for MMF
Toluene-acetonitrile-glacial acetic acid (7.0 : 2.9 : 0.1, v/v/v)	0.61	0.50	0.38	All three drugs baseline resolved Symmetric peak shapes with no tailing

TAC : Tacrolimus; SRL : Sirolimus; MMF : Mycophenolate mofetil.

afforded baseline separation of all three analytes in toluene : acetonitrile (7 : 3, v/v). But to eliminate minor peak tailing for MMF, addition of glacial acetic acid was warranted. Finally, the mobile phase consisting of toluene-acetonitrile-glacial acetic acid (7.0 : 2.9 : 0.1, v/v/v) provided symmetric peaks and baseline separation of TAC (R_f 0.61), SRL (R_f 0.50) and MMF (R_f 0.38). There was no evidence of tailing for any of the analytes as shown in Fig. 3. The details of trials conducted with different eluting solvent systems are summarized in Table 1.

The solid phase extraction procedure for TAC and SRL from human whole blood was based on our previous work with UPLC-MS/MS technique^{25,32}. Both the drugs were determined in blood samples as their absorption is variable and are found at very low concentration in plasma samples. The recovery obtained was consistent and quantitative for both the analytes across three QC levels (92.91–96.61%). Unlike TAC and SRL, MMF was separated from plasma samples by simple protein precipitation with acetonitrile to afford precise recovery.

Validation results :

The calibration curves showed good linearity ($r^2 \geq$

0.9994) over the concentration range of 500–4000 ng/band for TAC and SRL, and 200–1500 ng/band for MMF in neat samples as shown in Table 2. For biological samples, the peak area ratio versus the concentration plotted gave $r^2 \geq 0.9979$ for TAC, SRL and MMF. The LOD and LOQ for the analytes were calculated from the slope of the calibration lines and the standard deviation of the intercept. The results for neat solutions (aqueous samples) and in biological fluids are presented in Table 2.

The specificity of the method was assessed by analyzing the bands (in terms of R_f values) obtained for the samples with those of standards and the results obtained were in good correlation. The peak purity of TAC, SRL and MMF was established by comparing three different positions of the chromatograms, peak start, peak apex and peak end. The results found were in close agreement for all three analytes. Further, for blood/plasma samples the selectivity was evaluated by analyzing blank blood/plasma samples and samples spiked at medium QC level as shown in Fig. 4. The densitograms show no interference of endogenous components at the R_f values of the analytes. Also there was no change in the R_f values in biological samples for the three analytes.

Fig. 3. HPTLC densitograms of tacrolimus, sirolimus and mycophenolate mofetil at (A) 2000 ng/band (R_f 0.61 \pm 0.02), 2000 ng/band (R_f 0.50 \pm 0.02) and 750 ng/band (R_f 0.38 \pm 0.01) concentration, (B) in tablet formulation, 1000 ng/band, 1000 ng/band and 500 ng/band respectively.

Table 2. Linear regression and statistical data for tacrolimus, sirolimus and mycophenolate mofetil

Parameter	Tacrolimus		Sirolimus		Mycophenolate mofetil	
	Neat samples	Blood samples	Neat samples	Blood samples	Neat samples	Plasma samples
Wavelength (nm)	210		210		210	
Concentration range (ng/band)	500–4000		500–4000		200–1500	
R_f values (mean \pm SD) ^a	0.61 \pm 0.02	0.60 \pm 0.01	0.50 \pm 0.01	0.51 \pm 0.02	0.38 \pm 0.01	0.38 \pm 0.01
Intercept (mean \pm SD) ^a	3.257 \pm 0.485	3.805 \pm 0.478	1.312 \pm 0.916	1.625 \pm 0.902	5.460 \pm 1.751	6.073 \pm 1.630
Slope of calibration line (S) (mean \pm SD) ^a	0.094 \pm 0.015	0.073 \pm 0.009	0.072 \pm 0.006	0.065 \pm 0.006	0.229 \pm 0.037	0.187 \pm 0.028
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9999	0.9997	0.9994	0.9986	0.9998	0.9979
LOD (ng/band) 3.3 s/S	16.97	21.63	41.99	45.79	25.22	28.76
LOQ (ng/band) 10 s/S	51.59	65.48	127.22	138.75	76.42	87.15

^aMean values obtained from five calibration curves within the linearity range; LOD : Limit of detection; LOQ : Limit of quantitation; s : Standard deviation of the intercept.

The intra-day and inter-day precision (% RSD) for neat samples and in biological samples across three QC levels varied from 0.34–5.22% and 0.32–4.07% respectively for the three analytes (Table 3). The repeatability

Fig. 4. HPTLC densitograms of (A) blank biological fluid, (B) blank plasma/blood sample spiked with tacrolimus (1200 ng/band), sirolimus (1200 ng/band) and mycophenolate mofetil (500 ng/band).

Table 3. Intra-day and inter-day accuracy and precision data for tacrolimus, sirolimus and mycophenolate mofetil

Conc. (ng/band)	Intra-day (<i>n</i> = 6)			Inter-day (<i>n</i> = 6)		
	Mean conc. found ± SD	Precision (% RSD)	Accuracy (%)	Mean conc. found ± SD	Precision (% RSD)	Accuracy (%)
Neat samples						
Tacrolimus						
1200	1196 ± 8.0	0.67	99.67	1199 ± 11.7	0.97	99.92
2000	1989 ± 15.3	0.77	99.45	1992 ± 12.3	0.62	99.60
3200	3213 ± 10.9	0.34	100.41	3196 ± 10.5	0.33	99.87
Sirolimus						
1200	1192 ± 9.2	0.77	99.33	1189 ± 11.8	0.99	99.08
2000	1985 ± 17.8	0.89	99.25	1984 ± 25.8	1.30	99.20
3200	3190 ± 10.9	0.34	99.69	3205 ± 10.1	0.32	100.16
Mycophenolate mofetil						
500	494 ± 9.2	1.86	98.80	492 ± 9.7	1.97	98.40
750	742 ± 12.5	1.68	98.93	747 ± 7.8	1.04	99.60
1200	1186 ± 21.4	1.80	98.83	1193 ± 16.6	1.39	99.42

Table-3 (contd.)

Biological samples						
Tacrolimus (human blood)						
1200	1185 ± 61.9	5.22	98.75	1149 ± 38.1	3.32	95.75
2000	1947 ± 45.8	2.35	97.35	2034 ± 56.5	2.78	100.70
3200	3168 ± 32.9	1.04	99.00	3128 ± 62.9	2.01	97.75
Sirolimus (human blood)						
1200	1225 ± 36.0	2.94	102.10	1156 ± 46.0	3.98	96.32
2000	1945 ± 15.2	0.78	97.25	1969 ± 17.1	0.87	98.46
3200	3089 ± 41.7	1.35	96.53	3058 ± 53.2	1.74	95.57
Mycophenolate mofetil (human plasma)						
500	477 ± 21.8	4.58	95.42	483 ± 19.6	4.07	96.53
750	730 ± 16.8	2.31	97.31	719 ± 18.5	3.42	95.85
1200	1175 ± 14.8	1.26	97.99	1176 ± 30.3	2.58	98.01

SD : Standard deviation, RSD : Relative standard deviation; *n* : Number of replicates.

of sample application and measurement of peak area were determined in six replicates. For both the parameters, the precision (% RSD) was consistently less than 2.0% (Table 4). The accuracy (recovery) for neat samples was determined by the standard addition technique. This was done at three levels, 80, 100 and 120% of pre-analyzed low QC samples. For biological samples, the absolute recovery was determined by comparing the peak areas of freshly prepared (extracted) samples with neat standard solutions having identical concentration at three QC levels. The detailed results are presented in Table 5.

The stability of the stock solution and working solution of analytes were checked for short term stability at room temperature and long term stability at 5 °C. The samples for short term and long term stability were stable

for a minimum period of 24 h and 45 days respectively. Whole blood/plasma sample stability was evaluated by measuring the area response of stability samples against freshly prepared comparison standards with identical concentration at low and high QC levels. Bench top stability at 25 ± 1 °C, freeze-thaw stability, processed sample stability at 5 °C and long term stability (at -70 °C) was performed at both the QC levels in six replicates. The results indicate no significant change in the stability of the analytes under any condition (Table 6).

The method robustness studied under five different conditions, namely by changing the composition of mobile phase components, volume of the mobile phase, chamber saturation time, time from band application to chromatography and from chromatography to band scanning

Table 4. Results of repeatability studies for the proposed HPTLC method (*n* = 6)

Drug	Amount spotted (ng/band)	Measurement of peak area ^a		Sample application ^b	
		Amount found (ng/band ± SD)	Precision (% RSD)	Amount found (ng/band ± SD)	Precision (% RSD)
Tacrolimus	1200	1190 ± 12.6	1.06	1186 ± 12.5	1.05
	2000	1986 ± 17.8	0.89	1982 ± 24.6	1.24
	3200	3179 ± 24.9	0.78	3185 ± 27.7	0.87
Sirolimus	1200	1185 ± 19.9	1.68	1180 ± 23.1	1.96
	2000	1974 ± 15.2	0.77	1981 ± 19.6	0.99
	3200	3228 ± 29.1	0.90	3176 ± 35.6	1.12
Mycophenolate mofetil	500	487 ± 8.3	1.70	483 ± 8.1	1.68
	750	732 ± 8.1	1.11	755 ± 9.5	1.26
	1200	1192 ± 15.1	1.27	1186 ± 21.5	1.81

^aOne spot is scanned six times; ^bSix spots were analyzed once; SD : Standard deviation; RSD : Relative standard deviation; *n* : Number of replicates.

Table 5. Recovery of drugs in dosage forms by standard addition method and in human plasma ($n = 6$)

Tablet formulation	Amount of drug taken (ng/band)	Amount of pure drug added (ng/band)	Total amount found (ng/band \pm SD)	Precision (% RSD)	Recovery of pure drug (%)
Standard addition method for dosage form :					
Prograf [®] (Tacrolimus)	1200	960	2142 \pm 22.3	1.04	98.13
	1200	1200	2381 \pm 31.9	1.34	98.42
	1200	1440	2624 \pm 24.4	0.93	98.89
Rapamune [®] (Sirolimus)	1200	960	2147 \pm 27.5	1.28	98.65
	1200	1200	2423 \pm 15.5	0.64	101.9
	1200	1440	2631 \pm 45.5	1.73	99.37
Cellcept [®] (Mycophenolate mofetil)	500	400	894 \pm 12.8	1.44	98.50
	500	500	990 \pm 10.8	1.09	98.00
	500	600	1089 \pm 9.6	0.88	98.16
In spiked biological samples :					
	QC level (ng/band)	Mean conc. found (ng/band \pm SD)	Precision (% RSD)	Recovery (%)	Mean recovery (%)
Tacrolimus in human blood	1200	1117 \pm 35.4	3.17	93.12	93.48
	2000	1889 \pm 94.6	5.00	94.45	
	3200	2973 \pm 79.4	2.67	92.91	
Sirolimus in human blood	1200	1132 \pm 36.9	3.26	94.32	94.69
	2000	1933 \pm 79.6	4.12	96.61	
	3200	2980 \pm 38.1	1.28	93.14	
Mycophenolate mofetil in human plasma	500	483 \pm 15.3	3.16	96.51	96.52
	750	730 \pm 20.3	2.78	97.37	
	1200	1148 \pm 10.2	0.89	95.68	

SD : Standard deviation, RSD : Relative standard deviation; n : Number of replicates.**Table 6.** Stability data of tacrolimus, sirolimus and mycophenolate mofetil in biological samples under different conditions ($n = 6$)

Storage conditions	Tacrolimus			Sirolimus			Mycophenolate mofetil		
	Nominal conc. (ng/band)	Accuracy (%)	Precision (% RSD)	Nominal conc. (ng/band)	Accuracy (%)	Precision (% RSD)	Nominal conc. (ng/band)	Accuracy (%)	Precision (% RSD)
Bench top stability at room temperature, 9 h	1200	97.32	3.36	1200	95.67	2.56	500	94.67	4.37
	3200	96.37	1.37	3200	93.98	2.26	1200	95.45	3.98
Freeze-thaw stability at -70 °C, three cycles	1200	94.64	2.67	1200	97.64	4.34	500	98.76	2.83
	3200	98.55	4.13	3200	98.76	1.77	1200	99.36	0.56
Processed sample stability at 5 °C, 36 h	1200	95.37	3.98	1200	99.43	2.14	500	98.21	3.79
	3200	96.53	2.73	3200	101.57	4.63	1200	100.42	4.62
Long term stability at -70 °C, 60 days	1200	97.35	0.65	1200	96.52	1.81	500	96.47	0.77
	3200	95.60	1.34	3200	94.96	1.24	1200	98.71	1.04

RSD : Relative standard deviation; n : Number of replicates.

proved that small but deliberate changes in the analytical conditions does not affect the performance of the method significantly as evident from the precision values in the measurement of peak area of the analytes (Table 7).

Further, the % assay results of TAC ($100.08 \pm 0.61\%$), SRL ($98.90 \pm 1.71\%$) and MMF ($99.88 \pm 0.62\%$) from their pharmaceutical formulations prove that the newly developed and validated method is suitable for the analy-

Table 7. Results for robustness of the method ($n = 4$)

Condition	Tacrolimus (2000 ng/band)		Sirolimus (2000 ng/band)		Mycophenolate mofetil (750 ng/band)	
	Standard deviation	Precision	Standard deviation	Precision	Standard deviation	Precision
	of peak area	(% RSD)	of peak area	(% RSD)	of peak area	(% RSD)
Mobile phase composition (± 0.2 mL)	15.58	0.78	19.58	0.99	13.34	1.34
Mobile phase volume ($\pm 3.0\%$)	24.13	1.21	14.76	0.75	17.86	1.80
Chamber saturation time (± 4.0 min)	15.04	0.75	16.41	0.83	11.94	1.20
Time from spotting to chromatography (10.0 min)	16.72	0.84	13.85	0.70	14.74	1.49
Time from chromatography to scanning (10.0 min)	18.25	0.91	19.32	0.97	15.34	1.54

RSD : Relative standard deviation; n : Number of replicates.

sis of these analytes without any interference from the excipients.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

Reference standards of tacrolimus (TAC, FK-506, 99.5%), sirolimus (SRL, 99.4%) and mycophenolate mofetil (MMF, 98.0%) were obtained from Biocon Ltd. (Bangalore, India). HPLC grade toluene, acetonitrile and glacial acetic acid were purchased from E. Merck (Mumbai, India). Aluminium-backed HPTLC pre-coated silica gel plates 60 F₂₅₄ (20 cm × 10 cm, 200 µm layer thickness) were procured from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). Pharmaceutical formulations, Prograf[®] (5 mg tacrolimus) and Rapamune[®] (2 mg sirolimus) were purchased from United Biotech (New Delhi, India), while Cellcept[®] (500 mg mycophenolate mofetil) tablets were procured from Novartis Pharmaceuticals (New Jersey, USA). LiChrosep[®] Sequence (30 mg, 1 cc) solid phase extraction (SPE) cartridges were obtained from Merck Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai, India). Blank human plasma in K₃EDTA was obtained from Supratech Micropath (Ahmedabad, India) and blank human blood was procured from Cadila Pharmaceuticals Ltd. (Ahmedabad, India) and stored at -20 °C until use.

Chromatography instrumentation and conditions :

The HPTLC system (CAMAG, Muttenz, Switzerland) consisted of a TLC Scanner III, Linomat V auto-sprayer connected to a nitrogen cylinder and a plate heater. The plates were washed with methanol and activated at 105 °C for 20 min prior to use. The calibration standards

(CSs), quality controls (QCs) and sample solutions were applied to the plates with a Hamilton micro liter syringe using Linomat V sample applicator as bands, having 6 mm width and 6 mm apart. The sample application speed was set at 10 mm/s. The distance from the plate side edge and the bottom of the plate was 10 mm respectively. After the plates were air dried, linear ascending chromatography was carried out using toluene : acetonitrile : glacial acetic acid (7.0 : 2.9 : 0.1, v/v/v) as the mobile phase in a 20 cm × 10 cm twin-through glass chamber (CAMAG), which was pre-saturated with mobile phase for 15 min at 25 ± 1 °C and 60 ± 5% relative humidity. The development distance was 8.0 cm and the development time was 20 min. The densitometric scanning was performed in the absorbance-reflectance mode at 210 nm after scanning between 200–400 nm using a deuterium lamp. The slit dimensions were 5 mm length and 0.45 mm width, with a scanning rate of 20 mm/s. Each track was scanned three times and baseline correction was used. The winCATS software version 1.4.2 (CAMAG) was used to control the operating parameters during the entire experiment.

Preparation of stock solutions and calibrators :

Separate standard stock solutions of TAC (1000 µg/mL), SRL (1000 µg/mL) and MMF (1000 µg/mL) were prepared by dissolving requisite amounts in methanol. Further, working solutions having concentration 200 µg/mL for TAC and SRL and 100 µg/mL for MMF were prepared in methanol for band spotting. For preparation of calibration plots, 2.5, 5.0, 7.5, 10.0, 12.5, 15.0 and 20.0 µL of TAC and SRL and 2.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0, 12.5 and 15.0 µL of MMF were applied by over spotting

on TLC plates to have concentration in the range of 500–4000 ng/band for TAC and SRL respectively and 200–1500 ng/band for MMF. The plates were developed and scanned as described in Section 2.2. Similarly, QC samples were prepared at 1200 (low), 2000 (medium) and 3200 ng/band (high) for TAC and SRL respectively and 500 (low), 750 (medium) and 1200 ng/band (high) for MMF.

For preparation of spiked blood/plasma calibration samples, suitable aliquot from respective stock solutions was added to 0.5 mL drug free blood/plasma to obtain concentration in the range of 500–4000 ng/band for TAC and SRL respectively and 200–1500 ng/band for MMF. The concentration of QC samples for biological samples was identical with the neat solutions for all three analytes.

Solid phase extraction of tacrolimus or sirolimus from whole blood :

To a 500 μ L spiked blood sample (CSs and QCs), 500 μ L, 0.1 M zinc sulphate solution was added to lyse the cells, followed by vortex mixing for 1.0 min. After centrifugation for 5.0 min at $1811 \times g$, the supernatant was separated and subjected to SPE on Lichrosep Sequence cartridge, previously equilibrated with 1.0 mL of methanol followed by 1.0 mL of water. The cartridge was first washed with 1.0 mL, 10% acetic acid in water and then with 1.0 mL, 10% methanol in water. The elution of TAC/SRL was carried with 1.0 mL methanol in pre-labeled vials. The solvent was then evaporated to dryness in a thermostatically controlled water-bath maintained at 40 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The dried sample was reconstituted with 500 μ L methanol, briefly vortexed and 10 μ L was used for band spotting on TLC plates.

Sample preparation of mycophenolate mofetil from human plasma :

Prior to analysis all plasma samples (CSs and QCs) were thawed and allowed to equilibrate at room temperature. To an aliquot of 500 μ L of spiked plasma samples, 500 μ L acetonitrile was added and vortexed for 2.0 min. The samples were centrifuged at $1431 \times g$ for 10 min at 10 °C. Consequently, the supernatant was transferred into pre-labeled tubes, briefly vortexed and 10 μ L was used for band spotting on TLC plates.

Method validation :

The method was validated in accordance with the ICH guidelines for linearity, range, limits of detection and

quantitation, accuracy (recovery), precision, and robustness⁵³. The linearity was determined by plotting five independent analytical curves, each having seven point concentrations in the range of 500–4000 ng/band (500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500, 3000 and 4000 ng/band) for TAC and SRL and 200–1500 ng/band (200, 400, 600, 800, 1000, 1250 and 1500 ng/band) for MMF. The peak areas of the chromatograms were plotted versus the respective concentration of the drugs to obtain the analytical curves. The results were subjected to regression analysis by the least squares method to calculate the calibration equations.

To determine the specificity of the method, a solution of analytical placebo (a mixture all tablet excipients) was prepared and assessed for any possible interference at the retention time of the analytes by the developed method. The spots for all three drugs were confirmed by comparing the R_f values and spectra of the sample spots with those of standard drugs. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were evaluated from the standard deviation of the response (y-intercepts of regression lines) and the slope from five analytical curves using the expressions, $LOD = 3.3 s/S$ and $LOQ = 10 s/S$, where 's' is the standard deviation of the response and S represents the slope of the calibration curve.

To study the intra-day and inter-day precision of the method, six replicates of the mixed standards of the analytes at three QC levels were analyzed on the same day and on three consecutive validation days respectively. Precision (%RSD) for method repeatability was determined by measurement of peak area at low, medium and high QC levels without changing the position of the plate. Repeatability of sample application was assessed by spotting the analytes six times and analyzing them once.

The accuracy (recovery) for neat samples was determined by standard addition method. This parameter was studied by addition of standard drug solution at three different levels, 80, 100 and 120%, to pre-analyzed sample solution in six replicates. Densitograms were obtained and the peak areas were assessed. The concentrations of each drug and thereby the recovery was calculated from respective calibration curves.

The robustness of an analytical procedure refers to its ability to remain unaffected by small but deliberate varia-

tions in method parameters and provides a measure of its reliability for routine analysis. Method robustness was proved under five different conditions, by changing the composition of mobile phase components toluene-acetonitrile (6.9 : 2.9, 6.8 : 2.8 and 7.1 : 3.1, v/v), volume of the mobile phase ($\pm 3.0\%$), chamber saturation time (± 4.0 min), time from band application to chromatography and from chromatography to band scanning (± 10.0 min).

Assay of tablet formulation :

To ascertain the content of Prograf[®] (5.0 mg TAC), Rapamune[®] (2.0 mg SRL) and Cellcept[®] (500 mg MMF), 20 tablets of each were weighed and ground to fine powder separately. An amount equivalent to 5.0 mg of TAC, 2.0 mg of SRL and 500 mg MPA were transferred into separate 10 mL volumetric flask containing 5 mL methanol, sonicated for 30 min and then diluted with methanol. After filtration, a working solution having concentration of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of TAC, 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of SRL and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of MPA were prepared by diluting the stock solution with methanol and 10 μL was applied to the plates in six replicates. Subsequent to chromatographic development, peak areas of the bands were measured at 210 nm and the amount of each drug present in the tablet was estimated from the regression equations.

Conclusion

This is the first HPTLC method for the simultaneous determination of TAC, SRL and MMF in their pharmaceutical formulations and also from biological fluids. The developed method is highly selective and robust and is extensively validated as per the ICH guidelines. The statistical data proves that the method is suitable for analyzing TAC, SRL and MMF in their pure form and in pharmaceutical preparations without any interference from the excipients. The validation data suggests that the proposed densitometric method is reproducible, accurate and precise and can be readily applied for *in vivo* studies.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge Department of Chemistry and Zoology, Gujarat University for providing the instrumentation and infrastructure facility to carry out this work.

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